

Development of *N. atrovirens* on different host plants^a, South Cotabato, Philippines, 1985.

Host plant	Nymphs becoming adults (%)	Developmental period (d)	Nymphal longevity ^b (d)
<i>C. rotundus</i>	85	18	10.3 a
<i>C. iria</i>	40	19	18.7 a
<i>C. compressus</i>	—	—	13.7 b
<i>C. brevifolius</i>	—	—	12.6 b
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	—	—	4.5 c
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	—	—	5.0 c
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	—	—	5.3 c
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	—	—	1 d
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i>	—	—	1 d
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	—	—	1 d
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	—	—	1 d
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	—	—	1 d
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	—	—	1 d
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	—	—	4.7 c

^aAv of 4 replications, 10 1st instars/replication. ^bSeparation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

confirmed in a trial where it died on 200 rice varieties from IRRI's germplasm collection. *N. atrovirens* may significantly reduce *C. rotundus* growth, and has potential as a biocontrol agent for that weed. *J*

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Field evaluation of commercial insecticides for controlling yellow stem borer (YSB) in the Philippines

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Most modern rices have low to moderate resistance to YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas*. Insecticides are needed to control high YSB populations. We evaluated commercial insecticides for YSB control in the IRRI greenhouse, and then tested them in fields at the MRRTC, which is a YSB hot spot in dry season (Dec-Mar).

In 1980, we evaluated 15 foliar sprays and 8 granular insecticides on susceptible IR29. A foliar spray of chlorpyrifos + BPMC controlled deadhearts most effectively; and endosulfan and azinphos ethyl effectively controlled whiteheads (Table 1). Granular treatments showed fewer deadhearts with carbofuran (Table 2). Diazinon also was effective up to 20 d after treatment. No treatment significantly decreased whiteheads.

In 1981, 15 insecticides were applied as sprays and 4 as granules. Carbofuran granules prevented deadhearts most effectively and triazophos effectively controlled whiteheads (Table 3).

Table 1. YSB control with 15 foliar sprays, MRRTC, Philippines, 1980 DS.^a

Treatment ^b	Deadhearts (%)		Whiteheads (%)
	20 DT	40 DT	115 DT
Chlorpyrifos + BPMC 3 1.5 EC	6.9 a	2.8 a	4.8 ab
Monocrotophos 16.8 EC	7.3 ab	12.8 cd	3.2 ab
Endosulfan 35 EC	9.1 abc	14.9 cde	2.6 a
Fenthion 50 EC	9.8 abc	12.6 cd	3.6 ab
Carbophenothion 40 EC	9.9 abc	17.0 cdef	4.4 ab
<i>B. thuringiensis</i>	10.2 abc	18.1 def	5.6 ab
Diazinon 20 EC	10.5 abc	15.8 cdef	2.6 a
Phosphamidon 50 EC	10.7 abc	7.7 b	3.3 ab
Phosmet 50 WP	10.9 abc	19.7 ef	4.9 ab
Azinphos ethyl 40 EC	11.1 abc	11.1 bc	2.5 a
Fenitrothion 30 EC	11.1 abc	12.1 bcd	4.6 ab
Metalkamate 23 EC	11.3 abc	15.3 cdef	6.7 b
Dimethoate 40 EC	12.2 abc	16.7 cdef	5.2 ab
Untreated check	13.1 abc	22.6 f	3.9 ab
Methomyl 19.8 EC	13.4 abc	17.0 cdef	3.0 ab
BPMC 50 EC	14.4 c	14.6 de	5.2 ab

^aAv of 4 replications. Separation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. DT = days after transplanting. ^bAll insecticides were applied at 0.75 kg ai/ha except *B. thuringiensis*, which was applied at 0.4 kg formulation (600 IU/mg) per ha. Insecticides were applied at 10, 25, 45, 60, and 75 DT.

Table 2. YSB control with granular insecticides,^a MRRTC, Philippines, 1980 DS.

Treatment ^b	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Deadhearts		Whiteheads (%)
		20 DT	40 DT	115 DT
Carbofuran 3 G (SI)	1.0	1.4 ab	0.2 a	3.7 a
Carbofuran 3 G	1.0	1.0 ab	0.7 a	3.0 a
Gamma BHC + carbaryl 6 + 6 G	1.0	3.5 bc	11.6 d	4.6 a
Diazinon 5 G	1.0	0.6 a	5.4 bc	4.2 a
Gamma BHC + MIPC 6 + 4 G	1.0	1.9 ab	7.2 cd	5.0 a
Carbofuran 3 G	1.5	0.3 a	0.1 a	3.2 a
Gamma BHC + carbaryl 8 + 8 G	1.5	5.6 c	5.9 bc	3.4 a
Diazinon 5 G	1.5	0.9 a	3.5 b	4.4 a
Gamma BHC + MIPC 6 + 4 G	1.5	4.7 c	5.6 bc	3.0 a
Control	—	6.1 c	18.0 e	3.8 a

^aAv of 4 replications. Separation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. ^bAll treatments were applied to field water, except one treatment of carbofuran, which was soil incorporated (SI) before transplanting. Insecticides were applied at 10, 25, 45, 60, and 75 d after transplanting (DT).

Table 3. YSB control with insecticides,^a MRRTC, Philippines, 1981 DS.

Treatment ^b	Application method	Deadhearts (%)		Whiteheads (%)
		20 DT	40 DT	
Chlorpyrifos + BPMC	Spray	11.1 a	8.1 bc	7.5 cd
Triazophos	Spray	12.1 ab	8.4 b	1.7 a
Diazinon	Spray	14.2 abc	24.0 def	5.8 abcd
<i>B. thuringiensis</i> ^c	Spray	15.0 abc	32.1 fgh	6.1 abcd
Acephate	Spray	15.5 abcd	16.9 cde	3.8 abc
Azinphos ethyl	Spray	17.5 abcde	11.9 bcd	5.9 abcd
UCX 2001	Spray	18.4 abcdef	9.7 bc	4.6 abc
Monocrotophos	Spray	20.3 abcdefg	31.4 fgh	4.4 abc
Aktrion	Spray	23.8 bcdefg	36.2 fgh	7.9 cd
Phosphamidon	Spray	25.1 cdefg	29.7 fgh	7.0 bcd
MTMC	Spray	27.8 defg	31.4 fgh	7.0 bcd
Carbaryl XLR	Spray	29.3 efg	38.5 gh	6.1 abcd
Propoxur	Spray	29.7 efg	29.9 fgh	14.7 d
MIPC	Spray	29.8 efg	34.3 fgh	7.3 bcd
Endosulfan	Spray	31.0 efg	25.5 defg	7.3 bcd
BPMC	Spray	32.1 g	28.8 fgh	7.3 bcd
Carbaryl	Spray	33.7 g	26.8 efg	4.8 abc
Carbofuran	Granular broadcast	10.8 ab	0.6 a	1.9 ab
Diazinon	Granular broadcast	17.2 abcde	33.1 fgh	7.2 cd
Gamma BHC + carbaryl	Granular broadcast	25.1 cdefg	35.1 fgh	8.3 cd
Gamma BHC	Granular broadcast	27.8 cdefg	40.6 h	7.4 cd
Endosulfan	Granular broadcast	30.7 fg	32.8 fgh	5.4 abc
Untreated check		32.3 g	38.9 h	7.7 cd

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Insecticides were applied at 10, 25, 45, 60, and 75 d after transplanting (DT). All were applied as foliar spray except for the granular formulations which were broadcast into the field water. Sprays were applied at 0.75 kg ai/ha and granules at 1.0 kg ai/ha. ^c 30 billion spores/g.

Results show that spraying chlorpyrifos + BPMC and broadcasting triazophos and carbofuran granules on field water or incorporating them in soil provide the most effective YSB control. Soil incorporation of carbofuran before transplanting is the most efficient way to control deadhearts as only one application is required. But because it provides no control at whitehead stage, it may be necessary to spray triazophos or another insecticide for whitehead control. *ℒ*

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Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Herbicides for weed control in transplanted rice

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In the hill region of Karnataka, India, labor for manual weeding is scarce and expensive. Labor costs are \$1-1.25/d. Hence, manual weeding has become a problem. We evaluated herbicides for weed control in rice in 1983 kharif at RRS, Mudigere. Six herbicides at 2 application rates were compared with an unweeded check and hand weeding on 20 and 40 d after transplanting. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Herbicides were evenly mixed in sand

and applied 2 d after planting.

Weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Cyperus iria*, *Rotala indica*, *Scheonopectum corymbosus*, *Zizania* sp., *Geissaspis tenella*, *Eriocaulon hookerianum*, *Pennisetum* sp., *Sacciolepis interrupta*, *Eragrostis unioloides*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*.

Butachlor 1.0 kg ai/ha, thiobencarb 1.75 and 2.00 kg ai/ha, and pendimethalin 1.75 kg ai/ha controlled weeds most effectively (see table). Weed dry weights in those treatments were 0.18 to 0.25 g/m² and were comparable. The treatments also had significantly higher grain yield than the unweeded check. Weeds significantly reduced plant height, straw yield, and effective tillers. In the unweeded check, plant height was 60 cm, yield 6.5 t/ha, and effective tillers/plant 7. In treated plots they varied from 77 to 81 cm, 8.3 to 9.7 t/ha,

Herbicides for weed control in transplanted rice, Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weed dry weight (g/m ²) at harvest
Thiobencarb	2.00	5.8	0.2
Butachlor	1.25	5.1	0.5
Oxyfluorfen	0.12	5.5	2.3
Hand weeding 20 and 40 d after planting	—	5.5	0.2
Anilofos	0.50	5.4	1.0
Oxadiazon	0.50	5.2	1.7
Pendimethalin	2.00	5.2	1.1
Pendimethalin	1.75	5.1	0.2
Anilofos	0.40	5.1	2.4
Oxadiazon	0.40	5.1	1.2
Thiobencarb	1.75	5.0	0.2
Butachlor	1.00	4.8	0.2
Oxyfluorfen	0.09	4.7	3.5
Unweeded check	—	4.4	58.2
CD 5%		0.2	0.3

and 10 to 13 tillers/plant. Oxyfluorfen was toxic to rice. *ℒ*